

[Pre-experiment] Demographic questions

1. Which gender do you identify with: [Male, Female, Transgender, Non-binary, Others, I prefer not to declare]
2. How would you describe your experience contributing to open-source software projects? [Likert scale from no experience to experienced]
3. How would you describe your experience with GitHub? [Likert scale from no experience to experienced]
4. How would you describe your experience with GitHub bots? [Likert scale from no experience to experienced]
5. List the names of the GitHub bots you've had some experience with (optional question)

[Post-experiment - Scenario 1] Participants' perceptions

1. What do you need to do to have your contribution accepted?
2. What information did the bot(s) offer you?
3. How did the information from the bot(s) help you?
4. How much do you agree with the following statements [*Likert scale -- Strongly disagree; I disagree; neutral; I agree; strongly agree*]
 - 4.1. The bot(s) provided appropriate information for the purpose of the contribution.
 - 4.2. I could not understand the information offered by the bot(s).
 - 4.3. It was easy to understand the bot(s).
 - 4.4. I noticed the presence of the bot(s).
 - 4.5. The information offered by the bot was clear.
 - 4.6. The bot(s) offered information that was unnecessary.
 - 4.7. The amount of information offered by the bot(s) was appropriate.
 - 4.8. The bot(s) contributed to improve the efficiency of my work.

[Post-experiment - Scenario 2] Overview of the approaches (FunnelBot vs multi-bots)

1. Next, evaluate the interactions with the bots comparing the first and second activities:
 - a. In which of the interactions was it possible to obtain the information more objectively?
 - b. In which of the interactions was the fastest to find the information regarding the analyzed case?
 - c. In which of the interactions was the information arranged more appropriately to understanding the problem?
 - d. In which of the interactions was it possible to notice that the amount of information made it difficult to search for information?

- e. In which of the interactions was it possible to identify the bots present in the repository more easily?
2. What are the positives of interacting with multiple bots?
3. What are the positive points of interacting with ***the funnel bot?***
4. Do you have any additional comments about the experiment or the interaction with bots?